

“DETECTION OF MULTIDRUG RESISTANCE *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* ISOLATES FROM CLINICALLY RELEVANT SPECIMENS.”

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Abstract

Staphylococcus aureus is an important opportunistic pathogen responsible for a variety of diseases, ranging from minor skin infection to life treating systemic infection including endocarditis and sepsis. It is capable of secreting several exotoxins, which are associated with specific diseases. Multidrug Resistance is the state of decreased sensitivity to antibiotics that ordinarily causes growth inhibition or cell death. The emergence of multidrug resistance *S. aureus* with reduced susceptibility to many antibiotics is a serious and ongoing concern. The study was performed to determine the prevalence of multidrug resistance *S. aureus* in human clinical samples and to evaluate their sensitivity to different classes of antibiotics by Kirby-Bauer's disc diffusion method.

A total of 105 *S. aureus* isolates from various clinical specimens obtained over 06 month period in the Department of Microbiology, RMC, Pravara Instituted of Medical Science, Loni (MS). Identification of *S. aureus* isolates were carried out by phenotypic characterization. The isolates were subjected to antibiotic susceptibility testing by disc diffusion method, while 19 isolates were found multidrug resistance (MDR) and 86 were the susceptible. The 10 female patients had multidrug resistant *S. aureus* isolates, while male patients had 09. Pus sample had the highest prevalence of 12 multidrug resistant *S. aureus* isolates, while the least was from urine with 02 and there was no multidrug resistant *S. aureus* isolates, from Blood. The antibiotics susceptibility testing offers a simple and accurate identification of MDR profiles and could be used in clinical diagnosis as well as for the surveillance of the spread of antibiotic resistance determinants in epidemiological studies.

Keywords- *Staphylococcus aureus*, Antibiotics, MDR, Antibiotics susceptibility.

Introduction-

S. aureus is non sporulating, non motile gram-positive coccil bacterium, that is a member of the Firmicutes and is frequently found in the human respiratory tract and on the skin. It has an average diameter of 1µm and microscopically appears as grape like clusters. Its infection has become a global health problem particularly in hospital setup causing simple skin infection to life threatening infection. It can cause a range of illnesses from minor skin infection, such as pimples, impetigo, boils, cellulitis folliculitis, carbuncles, scalded skin syndrome and abscesses to life treating diseases such as pneumonia, meningitis, osteomyelitis, endocarditis, toxic shock syndrome, bacteremia and sepsis. *S. aureus* is capable of secreting several exotoxins, which are associated with specific diseases. It is estimated that 20% of the human population are long term carriers of *S. aureus* which can be found as part of normal skin flora and in anterior nares of the nasal passages.

Antibiotics played an important role to control and eradicate the epidemic diseases and saved many lives. However, the extensive and irrational use of antibiotics caused the emergence of antibiotics resistant pathogen. Resistant in bacteria against conventional antibiotics has become a serious health problem these days. Multidrug-resistant organisms (MDROs) are microorganisms that are resistant to one or more therapeutic classes of antimicrobial agents. The global emergence of multidrug-resistant bacteria is increasingly limiting the effectiveness of current drug and significantly causing treatment failure. Several factors may lead to the increase in antimicrobial resistant, such as hospital stay before ICU admission, hospitalization period before ICU admission, length of ICU stay, surgical ICU stay, the type of operation, previous antibiotic use, inappropriate use of antimicrobial drug and inadequate adherence to infection control practices. Data from the National Healthcare Associated Infections Surveillance (NHIS) system of the centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) show that 50% of healthcare associated *S. aureus* isolates are now multidrug resistant.

Material and Methods-

Collection of *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolates-

S. aureus isolates from clinical samples (Pus, Blood, Urine, Ear swab etc.) received in Department of Microbiology, RMC, Pravara Institute of Medical Science, Loni, India were collected and work carried out in College of Agriculture, Loni.

Phenotypic characterization for identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolates-

- 1) Gram Staining
- 2) Catalase Test
- 3) Coagulase Test
- 4) Mannitol Fermentation Test
- 5) Novobiocin and Polymyxin-B Sensitivity Test
- 6) Haemolysis Test
- 7) Glucose Test
- 8) Mannose Test
- 9) Sucrose Test

Antibiotic susceptibilities of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates to different antibiotics-

The antibiotic susceptibilities of the *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates to different antibiotics are tested using disc diffusion method. Antibacterial agents from different classes of antibiotics are used which included methicillin (M), erythromycin (E), vancomycin (VA), gentamycin (GEN), ampicillin (AMP), tetracycline(T), penicillin(P). (Himedia Labs, Mumbai, India).

Preparation and Maintenance of stock culture-

Phenotypically determined antibiotics resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates were inoculated on nutrient agar slants and incubated at 37°C. These cultures were stored in a refrigerator at 4°C. Fresh slopes cultures were prepared every 3-4 weeks until subjected to further study.

Result-

Phenotypic characterization for identification of *S. aureus* isolates.

Table1. Phenotypic characterization for identification of *S. aureus* isolates.

Sr. No	Confirmation test	Positive	Negative	Control
1.	Gram staining			
2.	Catalase			
3.	Coagulase			
4.	Sugar test a) Glucose b) Sucrose c) Mannose			

5.	Antibiotic susceptibility test by using Novobiocin and Polymyxin-B			
7.	Mannitol salt agar test			

Sr. No.	MDR Isolates of S. aureus	Gram Staining	Morphology Test	Catalase Test	Coagulase Test	Mannitol Fermentation Test	Novobiocin and Polymyxin-B Sensitivity Test		Haemolysis Test	Glucose Test	Mannose Test	Sucrose Test
							Nov.	Poly. B				
1	SA ₃	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
2	SA ₁₆	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
3	SA ₁₉	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
4	SA ₂₇	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
5	SA ₂₈	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
6	SA ₄₀	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
7	SA ₄₂	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
8	SA ₄₅	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
9	SA ₄₆	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
10	SA ₅₁	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
11	SA ₆₅	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
12	SA ₆₈	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
13	SA ₈₁	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
14	SA ₈₂	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
15	SA ₈₃	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
16	SA ₈₅	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
17	SA ₈₈	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
18	SA ₉₁	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+
19	SA ₉₅	+	Cocci	+	+	+	S	R	+	+	+	+

Antibiotic susceptibilities of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates to different antibiotics-

The phenotypic pattern of 105 *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates to different classes of antibiotics is tested using disc diffusion method. Out of total 105 *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates tested, 19 of them were found to be multidrug resistant and 86 were susceptible. The 10 female patients had multidrug resistant *S. aureus* isolates, while male patients had 09. Pus sample had the highest prevalence of 12 multidrug resistant *S. aureus* isolates, while the least was from urine with 02 and there was no multidrug resistant *S. aureus* isolates, from Blood.

Conclusion-

The phenotypic pattern of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates to different classes of antibiotics is tested using disc diffusion method. Out of total 105 *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates, 19 of them were found to be multidrug resistant and 86 were susceptible. A major factor in the emergence of antibiotic resistant organism is overuse of antibiotics in any setting, the hospital or community. MDR *S. aureus* will continue to evolve, hence the absolute necessity to control it before it really does get out of hand. Therefore action must be taken to reduce this problem. The ultimate goal is to offer appropriate and efficient antimicrobial drug to the patient. Limited treatment option for infection caused by such multidrug resistant *S. aureus* prompted the search for novel compound with a broad spectrum of activity and new therapeutic strategies.

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